

Impact of Counterfeit Products on Consumer Buying Behavior

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Abstract

During the past several decades, the counterfeiting industry has risen significantly. This study is intended to determine whether or not the social and psychological characteristics of consumers influence their decision to purchase counterfeit items. In this study, the purchase patterns and intentions of customers will be analyzed. This research paper also aims to identify research gaps by evaluating the elements that influence customers' decisions to purchase counterfeit products. We've prepared a survey to get an early start on our research, which focuses on the attitudes and behaviors of customers. Five demographic questions and seven questions pertaining to the two most important variables are included in the questionnaire (counterfeit products and customer purchasing behavior). Moreover, the sub-criteria were satisfaction, risk, grade, quality, and price. We conducted a survey of 106 individuals from Karachi's schools, businesses, social circles and random people from market industry participated in the study. The investigation's hypothesis and subject were evaluated using a regression model. According to a prior study, the purchase of counterfeit goods had minimal impact on customer behavior. Genuine brand products could benefit from a deeper understanding of customer behavior in order to develop more successful marketing strategies that encourage consumers to choose authentic brand products over counterfeit ones. After doing this research, it is now evident that how and on what factors the consumers in Karachi purchase counterfeit and imitated goods.

Keywords: Counterfeit Product, Consumer Buying Behavior, Purchase Intention, Factors.

Introduction

Background of the study

People faced a lot of economic and financial crises in the 1960s, due to World War II. They lack the financial capability to pick the best fashion products for them. That was the period when marketers began to manufacture very same types and sizes of products. People who have the worst financial situation, they began buying whatever they could get their hands on. After that, the period of marketers arrived, when marketers began making various items but focused on marketing what they had created, or in other words, the era of marketers. People first wanted to fulfill the basic needs, thus there was little knowledge of brands and branded products at the time. People were more conscious of diverse brands and premium fashion products as years moved. Even at that time, some consumer's incomes were sufficient to purchase luxury brands, while those whose incomes had fallen began searching for counterfeit goods. Products that are counterfeit are also known as knockoffs, replicas, copies, or fakes. As a result, the market for counterfeit products grew, and manufacturers began developing them to maximize their profit margins. Such products are precise replicas of the original product with a minor change that ordinary people will notice. As a result, the market for counterfeit products grew, and manufacturers began developing them to maximize their profit margins. Such products are precise replicas of the original product with a minor change that ordinary people will notice. As a result, counterfeit products are

those that have similar attributes or are somewhat different in comparison to the original or branded products (Eisend & Schuchert-Guler, 2006).

Luxury or prestigious items are those that give the impression of being unique. Good quality (Husic & Cicic, 2009). According to (Vigneron & Johnson, 2004), these product Dimensions such as distinctiveness, exclusivity, and expression can be used to distinguish them. Global counterfeiting has become one of the issues that are rapidly expanding in today's economy, with no signs of slowing down (Zhang et al., 2012). Counterfeit goods are having an impact on the economy. To put it another way: "manufacturing of duplicates that are exactly packed, including trademarks and labeling, duplicated to be the real object" (Penz & Stottinger, 2005). Imports of counterfeit and pirated goods are worth about half a trillion dollars per year, according to the OECD/EUIPO (2016), and account for about 2.5 percent of worldwide imports. Fake products account for up to 5% of all commodities imported into the European Union. Because of the low price and low consumer purchasing power, counterfeit products are bought (INC, 2018). Developing a conceptual framework for understanding consumer thoughts and behaviors becomes more challenging as the number of counterfeits soars. Consumer purchasing behavior and needs have been studied extensively in this area during the previous decade (Lysonski, Durvasula, & Watson, 2001; Solomon, 2003).

Food and beverage, fashion, jewelry, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and other personal care products are among the categories in which counterfeit products have been discovered. In addition to software and video games, they also provide other products (Europol, 2012). Contrary to common opinion, product counterfeiting has been a worry for business leaders from the beginning of recorded history. Due to their resemblance to the true, branded product, many counterfeit goods appear to consumers to be genuine. Each, however, is not intended to convince the consumer that the object they are purchasing is authentic. Nowadays, both deceptive and non-deceptive fakes can be discovered in the counterfeiting industry (Grossman & Sapiro, 1988; Bloch et. al., 1993). This problem is not confined to a few countries; rather, its prevalence is expanding globally (Gentry, Putrevu, & Shultz, 2006). Fake goods are on the rise nowadays. We need to understand customer purchasing habits better (Norum & Cuno, 2011) since the consumers are the main driving force behind counterfeiting. There is a pressing need to learn about consumers' willingness to purchase counterfeit goods at least once (Romani, Gistri, & Pace, 2012). Many specialists agree that location, economics, society, culture, demographics, and psychology affect customer attitudes and purchasing choices (Dibb, Simkin, Pride, & Ferrell, 2001).

Most counterfeit goods are consumed by buyers who mistakenly assume they purchase a natural product (Chiu & Leng, 2016). Due to various reasons, some individuals deliberately buy counterfeit luxury goods (Phau et al., 2009). For the most part, people avoid purchasing counterfeit luxury goods, and they are referred to as 'ethical reasons' shoppers (Purwanto et al., 2019). Sellers may also deceive buyers by offering counterfeit luxury goods (Pratt & Zeng, 2019). Consumers who are willing to buy counterfeit luxury products are not regarded to be engaging in misleading counterfeiting practices (Chiu & Leng, 2016). Moreover A luxury brand should also have a limited and restricted distribution and manufacturing in order to maintain high demand, and the service or product supplied by the brand should be unique in its own way (Nueno & Quelch, 1998; Kapferer & Bastien, 2009).

Because counterfeit goods are so widely available these days, they're posing a much more severe economic threat than previously; it impacts the economy negatively by causing employment losses. For businesses, counterfeiting leads to decreased turnover, worse return on investment and innovation, higher legal costs, and the development of intellectual property rights (IPR) protective equipment, as well as considerable brand equity loss. From a broader perspective, counterfeiting poses a hazard to customers and people by increasing the risk of faulty or fraudulent items, as well as inciting resistance toward products and organizations. It used to be that counterfeit items would have distinct names and styles, making it easy to tell them apart from the real thing. This issue has become worse in the twenty-first century, with illicit producers copying the originals and offering inferior goods at lower prices and with the same packaging, design, and logos (Kumar, 2015).

The elements that encourage the purchasing of counterfeit goods advantages in terms of money, personal or professional perceptions hedonic advantages and previous buying experiences ((Nia & Zaichkowsky, 2000; Gentry et al., 2000; Ha & Lennon, 2006.)"The trouble is the fraudulent items nowadays are higher quality and

better pricing than the actual brands," says the author. Do you believe this? (2016). Predicting behavior with high accuracy may be attributed to Ajzen (1985). This idea plays a significant role. Piracy is defined in this context as a specific individual's purpose to do so (or not to pirate). Attitude, subjective norm, and perceptions of behavior are all factors that influence intentions, according to Ajzen. Intentions measure a person's willingness to put out the effort necessary to carry out a particular behavior. When it comes to acquiring counterfeit goods, intentions are seen as an essential precursor to the actual act of doing so. This study will focus on this connection since prior research has shown a clear correlation between a counterfeiter's buying behavior and their aim.

Counterfeit luxury products are becoming more popular worldwide (Norum & Cuno, 2011). The manufacturing of items that are identical to the original product in terms of trademarks, labeling, and packaging, which consumers think to be genuine, is meant by counterfeiting (Patiro & Sihombing 2016). Counterfeit products and brands are a significant challenge for original producers since no product or brand is entirely safe (Lee & Workman, 2011). Only the items that have a well-known brand name are affected by counterfeiting, but so are the products' research and development, as well as their marketing (Hieke, 2010). In nations with tight legislation prohibiting the sale of counterfeit luxury goods, these commodities pose a danger to public health and the environment (World Trademark Review, 2010). When counterfeit goods become more prevalent, buyers' desire to acquire them grows as well (Bhatia, 2018). Counterfeit luxury goods are readily apparent in product categories with solid demand, and the production technique is affordable and widely available (Chiu & Leng, 2016).

It is true that counterfeiting costs original product and brand owners money, but it also threatens a significant number of jobs and boosts the cost of marketing authentic goods. It is probable that counterfeit amphetamines, tranquilizers, and birth control pills constitute a threat to consumer health (Chakraborty, Allred, & Bristol, 1996).

Overall, the focus of this study is on customers' attitudes on purchasing counterfeit luxury fashion products (CLFI) as well as their intent to acquire CLFI. More precisely, the research will look at whether there is a difference in attitude regarding acquiring CLFI whether one is taught about the personal harm counterfeits inflict versus the societal costs associated with counterfeit trade. In addition, various aspects that have been found to be essential in prior studies (e.g., subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and so on) will be reexamined in a Belgian setting. In addition, the relationship between price, quality, and perceived quality will be investigated (Dennis, 2010). Finally, the relationship between attitudes and intentions is examined in the context of counterfeiting.

Primary data will be gathered through a 12-question survey administered to a representative population sample. In universities and workplaces, a poll of 106 people was administered. It is also disseminated to relatives and friends. The hypothesis and research questions will be tested using the Regression model.

Scope of the Study

With the ability to better comprehend the customers' motivations and what motivates them to buy counterfeit products, the manufacturers of big brands and the marketers of those brands can make better marketing strategies. It can create product differentiation to motivate the buyer to buy the original product rather than spend money on fakes and counterfeit versions. Extending information about customers' purchasing habits about counterfeit goods in Karachi will benefit from this study's theoretical contributions.

Objectives of the Study

The goals of this research are to find out what is going on

- Why do people tend to use counterfeit products and not the original products?
- How and what causes the consumer and what effect it has on consumer buying behavior?

However, despite several investigations into the influence of counterfeit goods on consumer purchasing behavior, the image of these items remains ambiguous primarily. Consumers, it is said in the literature, purchase counterfeit goods to profit economically (Yoo & Lee, 2009).

Statement of the Problem

The quality of counterfeit luxury goods has steadily improved over the years, making it more difficult to tell the difference between imitation and authentic goods. It's widely accepted that pricing has always played a significant role in customers' purchasing counterfeit goods rather than authentic ones. Many are prepared to buy counterfeits to experience the excitement of purchasing an original product.

Research Questions

- Q- Is there a link between counterfeit goods and consumers' purchasing habits?
- Q- What's the amount of satisfaction you get compared to counterfeit product vs. original product?
- Q- Is it worth it buying counterfeit Products?

Significance of the Study

According to research published in peer-reviewed journals, consumers often purchase counterfeit goods to avoid paying the high price of genuine goods. Some researchers claim that the customer's age does not affect the purchase decision on intent to purchase counterfeits. Some researchers say that the young generation is primarily interested in buying fake products.

Research Gap

What motivates consumers to buy a counterfeit product, and how much satisfaction do they get?

Literature Review

Any items carrying, without a license, a trademark which cannot be differentiated in its basic elements from the trademark registered for such goods (OECD, 2009) are considered counterfeit trademark products. It is also defined as imitated or faked product which is made to be sold to their consumer. The history of counterfeit products is vast. Everyone is busy in making money by copying others products and making profit out of it without keeping in their mind that they may fraud their market. This kind of counterfeit goods is an illegal copy of an authentic brand, and its brand characteristics mirror those of the actual product, according to (Bian & Moutinho, 2009).

Counterfeit products originate and are marketed openly in Pakistan, one of the top 10 nations for counterfeit goods globally (Ahmad, Yousif, Shabeer, & Imran, 2014). Buying counterfeit items is encouraged by the ease with which they can be purchased online. It has been cited (Penz & Stöttinger, 2005; Chaudhry & Stumpf, 2011). To put it another way, counter-products are imitations or replicas of the original. We call them knock-offs. A counterfeit is a product that utilizes a brand without authorization from the trademark holder. The vendor is trying to benefit from the trademark owner reputation by creating or selling a counterfeit. Consumer items designed or marketed under another brand name without the brand owner permission are counterfeits and often of worse quality. Consumers are influenced by a variety of variables when they purchase counterfeit goods. Any product in any country is now susceptible to this affliction. Pfizer, the New York-based pharmaceutical firm that makes the anti-inflammatory medicine Ponstan, discovered that their product had been targeted by Colombian counterfeiters looking to profit illegally off the intellectual property of numerous well-known American businesses (Hopkins, 2003).

In a free-market economy, counterfeit items may cause significant harm. In addition, the unfair competition caused by counterfeit items puts future investment in research and development at risk. Lack of knowledge about the elements that encourage buyers to purchase and assess these counterfeit items is a significant problem (Cecilia Maldonado, 2005).

The majority of academics distinguish between deceptive and non-deceptive counterfeit items (Chakraborty, Allred, & Bristol, 1996). Counterfeit items are sold to unsuspecting customers who aren't aware that they aren't authentic (Phau & Teah, 2009). Counterfeiting that isn't deceptive, on the other hand, occurs when customers buy a product even though they know its not the original because of significant price differences, lower quality, or the fact that genuine manufacturers have included certain features that recognize originality.

The term blur counterfeiting was coined by Bian (2006) to describe a new sort of counterfeiting. Counterfeit goods may be discovered at any time and in any location. Even though many people purchase these items, many complain afterward about their poor quality. Despite this, the market for fakes has proliferated. We need to know why customers buy counterfeit items, and more particularly, is the price the only factor that swayed them from purchasing genuine products and acquiring counterfeit ones. We must look at how individuals demand luxury brands to feel more respected, seem more well-off, and live up to societal standards of what affluent people should look like, and how this affects their purchase decisions for genuine vs. counterfeit goods—the following year (Demetris Vrontis, 2020).

The deliberate procurement of counterfeits is seen as consumer misbehavior that deviates from widely accepted norms (Lee & Workman, 2011). Certain elements, such as culture, social, personal, and psychological, have an impact on a consumer's buying intentions. The cultural component includes the nation's culture, subcultures, and various socioeconomic classes, whereas the social dimension encompasses reference groups, everyday roles, family size, and status. Demographic elements such as age, income, employment, and living conditions are included in the personal component, whereas psychological dynamics include inspiration and style of thinking. Each of the four elements analyzed is made up of a combination of these dimensions. As positive attitudes and subjective norms rise, so does an individual's desire to purchase a certain product rise (Ajzen, 1991).

Purchase intention is seen to be a high-priority antecedent of human action since it indicates a person's readiness to carry out a certain behavior (Wilcox et al., 2009). People frequently attempt to improve their status in order to get more joy from obtaining goods. Research focuses on the attitude and action of customers who are using counterfeit products and ignore the non-users of counterfeit products (Davicik et al., 2018). Some studies sought to compare counterfeit purchasers and non-buyers based on individual characteristics such as demographics, social influence, and personality traits. Bloch et al. (1993) compared the demographics and self-image of real and counterfeit customers. In terms of demography, there was no difference amongst the respondents. In terms of self-esteem and self-confidence, counterfeit customers have lower self-esteem and self-confidence than genuine and private label purchasers, and they regard themselves as less well-off and successful. On the basis of demography, social influence, and personality qualities, Ang et al. (2001) sought to distinguish consumers from non-buyers of pirated CDs. On demographics, they discovered no differences. Furthermore, most studies divide consumers and non-users of counterfeits, treating each group as a homogenous population that would either buy or not buy counterfeit goods. Regardless of the product category, product qualities, or buying circumstance, consumers are categorized as either purchasers or non-buyers of counterfeits. Few studies take into account the possibility of several customer profiles based on various motives or features. Due to counterfeits, illegal and immoral character, many marketplaces do not publicly offer these items to the general public. Since the availability of counterfeits depends on the information that customers have and receive, consumers cannot exercise perfect control over their purchases (Lan et al., 2012). Consumers who have more access to counterfeit items will have a greater sense of control over their behavior, which may lead to a greater desire to acquire counterfeit goods (Prendergast et al., 2002; Chiu et al., 2014; Chiu & Leng, 2016; Armitage & Conner, 2001; Penz & Stottinger, 2005). Researchers have taken on the task of determining the elements that influence customers purchasing decisions regarding counterfeit items of all kinds. TPB has been utilized extensively as a fundamental paradigm for understanding customer's attitudes and buying behavior around counterfeit products (Chiu et al., 2014; Chiu & Leng, 2015, 2016).

Most counterfeit goods are purchased and consumed by customers who mistakenly believe that a product is genuine (Chiu & Leng, 2016). Some people buy counterfeit luxury products for a variety of reasons (Phau et al., 2009). Avoiding counterfeit luxury goods is generally seen as a sign of "good intentions" (Purwanto et al., 2019). Counterfeit luxury products are sold by some businesses to mislead customers (Pratt & Zeng, 2019). When a customer is willing to purchase fake luxury goods, the practice is referred to as "non-deceptive counterfeit purchasing" (Chiu & Leng, 2016). It has been determined that the transaction was not dishonest based on the reasons that led to the acquisition of counterfeit luxury items. It is the goal of this research to discover what drives non-deceptive counterfeiting in Karachi, Pakistan. Consumer behavior refers to the

conduct of customers when they purchase, use and evaluate things and services that they believe will meet their requirements and then discard them. Consumption-related purchases are examined in consumer behavior, which focuses on how people allocate their available resources (time, money, effort) to these purchases. When it comes to their purchasing habits, this encompasses everything from the products they buy and use to the frequency of their assets and the influence of their evaluations on their future purchases and how they dispose of their investments. This means that consumer behavior refers to how people acquire, use, and dispose of goods, services, concepts, and experiences (Bello, 2008).

Counterfeits are sold in the same packaging and labeling as the brand name and generic items. Because of this, people are frequently deceived into believing they are purchasing legitimate items. Imitating anything is known as counterfeiting. Counterfeit items are imitations of the genuine article, not the actual thing. Many counterfeit items aim to benefit from the inferior products' better value when they are made. Ethical/unethical intent is a person's purpose of engaging in a given behavior or not engaging in a specified behavior. One of the most compelling reasons for purchasing counterfeit goods is the brand's logo. People buy these items to elevate their social status (Grossman & Shapiro, 1988; Wilcox et al., 2009). Counterfeit goods are purchased to avoid getting overcharged while purchasing genuine goods. Another reason is that fake goods cost around a third or even a fourth as genuine ones. People tend to overlook the bad quality of these items because of this benefit (Tom et al., 1998; Wiedmann et al., 2012).

Theories

According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), an individual's purchasing behavior is influenced by their attitude toward a purchase. Researchers have researched a vast array of product categories and discovered that consumer preferences are not the sole factor influencing real behavior. Regarding the regulation of conduct, it is impossible to overstate the significance of attitudes, subjective norms, and self-perceptions. The predictive ability of attitudes, subjective standards, and the feeling of behavioral control vary per item (Ajzen, 1991; Armitage & Conner, 2001). The TPB has also shed light on the operations of persons who get counterfeit goods (Phau et al., 2009; Chiu et al., 2014; De Matos et al., 2007; Penz & Stottinger, 2005; Chiu & Leng, 2015, 2016). It has been discovered that the TPB is an effective instrument for examining how people make decisions while acquiring counterfeit goods, both voluntarily and unconsciously (Ajzen, 1991). When it comes to purchasing from a counterfeiter, purchasers are more likely to do so if they possess a positive attitude, certain criteria, and self-control. Positivity toward purchasing counterfeit goods increases the likelihood of doing so (Swami et al., 2009; Tom et al., 1998; Phau et al., 2009; Ang et al., 2001; Chiu et al., 2014; Wee et al., 1995). Customers' subjective expectations can affect their propensity to purchase counterfeit goods (De Matos et al., 2007; Penz & Stottinger, 2005; Phau et al., 2009; Ang et al., 2001; Tom et al., 1998; Rahman et al., 2011; Prendergast et al., 2002; Huang et al., 2015; Chiu et al., 2014). Because they support your behavior, your friends and family will push you to purchase counterfeit goods. The more well-known a product category is, the less likely buyers are to engage in such activity, especially if their relatives and friends disapprove (Lan. et al., 2012; Tang et al., 2014; Lord et al., 2001).

Perceived Quality

A person determines how well a product can meet customer expectations and demonstrate superiority over rival options (Hilton et al., 2004). Cheung and Prendergast (2006) characterize intangible product qualities, such as perceived quality, as eliciting an emotional response from consumers. Since it is centered on the demands of the consumer, perceived quality is a significant factor in purchasing decisions. It is customer-centric if the present view or experience of the consumer with the product is founded on this principle (Zeithaml et al., 1996). The perception of a product's quality may be influenced by other marketing factors, such as consumer satisfaction and purchase intent (Jang & Namkung, 2009). According to Bloch et al., the perceived quality of a product is based on universal dimensions and characteristics such as dependability and performance (1993). These perceptions are generated following the purchase of the product (Bian & Moutinho, 2011). Contrary to popular belief, counterfeit items are increasingly considered to be of equivalent quality to authentic goods due to their

striking resemblance and the usage of trademarks to differentiate them (Matos et al., 2007). Individuals are permitted to purchase counterfeit items even if their perceived quality is lower than that of authentic goods (Vida, 2007).

However, counterfeiters do not consider their items are inferior to authentic ones (Chaudhry & Stumpf, 2011). Even if businesses do not face monetary losses as a result of counterfeit goods, their brand's reputation and consumer trust may be harmed (Gentry et al., 2006). If counterfeit items are of decent quality, they have a certain cachet (Grossman & Shapiro, 1988). This indicates that consumers' purchase decisions are influenced by their perception of the quality of counterfeit items. Hence, this leads to the following hypothesis;

H1: The perceived quality of counterfeit goods influences a person's decision to buy.

Ethics

When it comes to consumer ethics, all that matters is whether or not the rest of society accepts and acknowledges a person's purchase decisions, intentions, and opinions (Ha & Lennon, 2006). A person's moral values may influence their purchasing decisions (Vitell, 2003). Individual ethical convictions were assessed using the idealism and relativism variables developed by Forsyth in 1980. When making moral judgements, relativists consider the situation's context rather than predetermined norms and goals (Forsyth, 1980).

Islamic philosophers have contributed significantly to the study of everyday morality and ethics (Ali, 2011). In Islam, ethical behavior is viewed as a soul-based trait that propels an individual to behave without doubt or care for the consequences of their actions (Ali & Al-Aali, 2015). When confronted with moral issues and need to make a decision, people go through three stages: seeing the circumstance, analyzing it from an ethical position, and creating solutions to the problem (Ha & Lennon, 2006). Consumer ethics guide the decisions of an individual, group, or organization when it comes to making purchases and consuming products and services (Sagar et al., 2011). Rather than emphasizing the customer's viewpoint, early research in marketing ethics concentrated on the principles of certain industries, such as sales, marketing research, advertising, and social marketing (Gino et al., 2010). Instead, consumer ethics have been the subject of research, especially in relation to the purchase of counterfeit goods (Eisend & Schuchert, 2006). Counterfeit products can have a detrimental influence on customers who place a high value on honesty and responsibility (Maldonado, 2005). Wilcox et al. (2009) found that consumers were less inclined to purchase counterfeit goods if they perceived the goods to be unethical (Vitell, 2003). Researchers discovered that some buyers justified their purchase of counterfeit goods by asserting that their own conduct was less offensive than that of the vendor. In this situation, moral relativism is demonstrated. Hence, this lead to the foundation of following hypothesis;

H2: Ethical issues have a favorable impact on a person's decision to buy counterfeit goods.

Status Consumption

Status is a measure of a person's social position, particularly in contrast to his or her peers (Eastman & Eastman, 2011). Examining a person's desire and ability to purchase expensive goods and services is one method for determining social position (Kempen, 2003 & Nia et al., 2000). Status symbols are consumed to the extent that a person's demand for social standing is satisfied (Eastman & Eastman, 2011). The possession of brand signifiers (e.g., items, visuals, services, and attitudes) allows membership in a particular social group and the formation of a network of interconnected images like things, visuals, services, and attitudes (Van Kempen, 2003, Ian et al., 2009).

To demonstrate their riches and social standing, some individuals emulate the exorbitant prices of well-known brands by purchasing counterfeit goods (Yoo & Lee, 2009 & Ergn, 2010). If they purchase a counterfeit luxury item, they may be able to claim the related status (Chaudhuri and Majumdar, 2006). It draws upon the work of Chaudhuri and Majumdar (2006). Others prefer to spend more on luxury products and pay more for an inconspicuous label (Ha and Tam, 2015). (2015). Though they purchase luxury goods for different reasons, the primary objective of both sorts of customers is the same: to enhance their own sense of self-worth (Chaudhry and Stumpf, 2011). Those with a strong sense of social standing are likely to seek out luxury labels, which symbolize wealth and social status (Park et al., 2008). This leads to the following hypothesis;

H3: Individual's intents to buy counterfeit goods are favorably influenced by their perceived status.

Low Price

At a fraction of the cost, counterfeit items outperform their original counterparts. People purchase luxury items for symbolic reasons due to their widespread admiration and widespread recognition (Ian et al., 2009). Due to price savings, consumers may neglect poor product quality and ethical issues while purchasing counterfeits (Norum and Cuno, 2011). Therefore, the price influences counterfeiters' purchasing intent, and pricing is the key means of grabbing buyers' attention (Ang et al., 2001, Penz et al., 2008, Chaudhry & Stumpf, 2011). Those who wish to make an impression on others should pay the greatest attention to their price sensitivity (Prendergast et al., 2002; Ha & Lennon, 2006; Furnham & Valgeirsson, 2007). As discovered by Huang et al. (2004), those who are more prices sensitive are more likely to acquire counterfeits. Due to the lower prices, individuals with fixed incomes will be more likely to purchase things. Hence, this leads to the following hypothesis;

H4: Low price positively affect an individual's intentions to purchase counterfeited products.

Conceptual Framework

Methodology

This literature analysis examined the numerous reasons why individuals purchase counterfeit products. The objective of this study is not the intent to purchase counterfeit items, but rather the examination of independent criteria (determinants). This study distinguishes between research analyzing the impact of dependent determinants (factors) on customer intent to purchase counterfeits and research examining the impact of same determinants on consumer attitude to purchase counterfeits. In many researches, both the effect of these variables on counterfeit purchase intention and the effect of these determinants on customer attitude regarding purchasing counterfeits are examined. In addition to the investigated mediators and moderators, this study uncovered additional indirect correlations.

Research Design

This research will examine the customer behavior and views of the fashion sector. The hypothesis of this study is that counterfeiting has no influence on purchasers. Consequently, this study is a sort of causal analysis designed to establish the relationship between counterfeiting in the fashion sector and consumer buying patterns.

Questionnaire

We have designed a questionnaire to gather primary data for this study based on customer behavior and attitudes. The questionnaire includes five demographic questions and seven questions related to counterfeit items and consumer purchasing habits for this study. The authors have further subdivided the primary variables into their sub-variables.

- Counterfeit Products (Independent Variable).
- Sub variables: Satisfaction, Risk
- Consumer Buying Behavior (Dependent Variable)
- Sub variables: Quality, Price

Population and Sample

The survey was conducted in the Karachi area of Clifton and DHA, which has a population of around 600k according to the following website,

(<https://www.citypopulation.de/en/pakistan/karachi/admin/>)

Our sample size is 267, as calculated from Rao soft, and we will be floating 300 questionnaires to people from different universities, banks, or any company.

Inclusion Criteria

We will select people of young age who know counterfeit products and fancy buying luxury products such as university students, people working at the banks or any company, or people with good income. We will submit the questionnaire to people aged 20 to 40.

Sampling Technique

People who were conveniently available at our institution and a few workplaces and friends and family members were given questionnaires to collect the data.

Statistical Technique

A regression model will be utilized to determine the influence of the independent variable, i.e., Consumer Buying Behavior, on the dependent variable, which is the purpose of this study, i.e., Counterfeit Products. $Y = \alpha + \beta X + \epsilon$ Where: Y = Fashion Industry X = Product Counterfeiting α and β = coefficients ϵ = error term.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile

The demographic profile we used in age is from 20 to 40 years, what is their gender, what’s their education Level, what’s their employment status, and last is their income range.

Table 1

		Frequency	Percent
Age	20-25	83	78.3
	26-30	17	16.0
	31-35	5	4.7
	36-40	1	.9
	Total	106	100.0

According to table 1, the people in the age of 20 to 25 have filled most of the questionnaire because this is the targeted audience who buy the counterfeit product.

Table 2

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	37	34.9
	Female	69	65.1
	Total	106	100.0

The table 2 shows that the responses were in greater numbers by the females than the males. This is because the female tends to use more counterfeit products such as bags and shoes.

Table 3

		Frequency	Percent
Education	College	16	15.1
	Undergraduate	59	55.7
	Graduate	19	17.9
	Master's	12	11.3
	Total	106	100.0

The table 3 shows that the undergraduates have filled our questionnaire more. This might be because this generation is more into fashion.

Table 4

		Frequency	Percent
Employment	Unemployed	43	40.6
	Employed	63	59.4
	Total	106	100.0

According to the table 4, the people who are employed were more responsive because the people who already have access to resources tends to be involved more in purchasing and spending.

Table 5

		Frequency	Percent
Income	0>25k	47	44.3
	25k>50k	15	14.2
	50k>75k	15	14.2
	Above 75K	29	27.4
	Total	106	100.0

According to the table 5, results show that the people having income of around 25000 have responded more because they find counterfeit products cheaper and easily accessible.

Gender
106 responses

• What's your age?
106 responses

Education
106 responses

Employment status

106 responses

Income

106 responses

Graphical Analysis

• What's the amount of satisfaction you get compared to the original product?

106 responses

• How likely can you tell the difference between a counterfeit product and original? 1 being the lowest and 5th the highest order.

106 responses

• Does the price of counterfeit product justify the price of original product?

106 responses

• Do you believe the quality of the counterfeit goods you buy are of high quality?

106 responses

• Would you buy the counterfeit product if it was of bad quality but low price?

106 responses

• Would you buy original product over counterfeit product if original product price were nearly same as of counterfeit product?

106 responses

• Would you buy the counterfeit product if it was of high quality but slighter lower price than the original product?

106 responses

Descriptive Analysis

Table 6

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Counterfeit Products(Mean)	106	1.00	5.00	3.6352	.74823	-.539	.235	.564	.465
Consumer buying behavior (mean)	106	1.00	5.00	2.7052	.80460	-.001	.235	-.002	.465

Reliability Analysis

Table 7

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Buying Behavior	.472	4
Counterfeit Products	.142	3

Cronbach's Alpha was used to determine whether or not the questionnaire was trustworthy. Cronbach Alpha's liberal cutoff is 0.6, whereas the strict cutoff is 0.7. Because our dependent variable came back at .472 and our independent variable came back at 0.142 (which is less than 0.6). We may conclude that our questionnaire was unreliable and that a more trustworthy one should have been utilized to get better results.

Correlation

Table 8

		cpttotal	cbbttotal
Counterfeit Product	Pearson Correlation	1	.157
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.108
	N	106	106
Consumer Buying Behavior	Pearson Correlation	.157	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.108	
	N	106	106

The correlation is statistically significant at a significance level of 0.01. (2-tailed) To verify the independence of our multiple variables, we use correlation. Our key variables, Consumer Buying Behavior and Counterfeiting Products have a 15.7% association. Results reveal that counterfeit goods and customer purchasing habits are not linked.

ANOVA

Table 9

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.679	1	1.679	2.633	.108 ^b
	Residual	66.296	104	.637		
	Total	67.975	105			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Counterfeit product

a. Dependent Variable: CBB

b. Predictors: (Constant),

CF According to our knowledge, the significance level (sig) is less than 0.01, which indicates it is significant at 1%. Aside from that, the ANOVA tells us about the model's overall significance and fit. F has a four-year cutoff. 2.633 is less than 4 in this case, so the value of F is less. Essentially, this suggests that the model is of no use. a significant model would have been found if F was at least four.

Table 10

Model	Coefficients				
	Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.091	.386		5.411 .000
	Counterfeit Prod	.169	.104	.157	1.623 .108

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer buying behavior

Indicator for CBB as a Dependent and this table illustrates the effect of counterfeit goods on customer purchasing habits. Coefficients of Counterfeit Items reveal a clear link between counterfeit products and consumers' purchases. If counterfeit items rise by one unit, consumers' purchasing behavior will increase by 169 units. Nearly two are within the acceptable range of "t" values. This demonstrates that the correlation is statistically significant. The sig value is less than or equal to 0.01, indicating that the connection is essential.

Table 11

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.157 ^a	.025	.015	.79841

a. Predictors: (Constant), Counterfeit Product

Hypotheses Assessment Summary

The null hypothesis H0 is rejected if the pace of growth of counterfeit products is one percent. Customers' purchasing habits would increase by 15.7% as a result. Based on our observations and research, we are inclined to accept H1, as there is a strong correlation between counterfeit goods use and consumer purchasing patterns.

Discussion

Various measures have been taken by the outdoor recreation goods business to prevent the invention, production, and distribution of counterfeit products. This study examines consumer perspectives on the purchase of counterfeit products. Using justifications for the purchase of counterfeits in other product categories, research indicates that consumers are aware of the safety and functionality hazards associated with outdoor recreation equipment. More risk-averse consumers are less inclined to acquire counterfeit items. As a result of the manufacturer's claims regarding product quality, perceived safety, and usefulness, buyers are more likely to purchase authentic goods. Manufacturers of recreational items must highlight the distinctive characteristics that set their products apart from the competition. Both the dangers of outdoor activities and the advantages of using high-quality items should be emphasized. To attract customers who are more prone to be terrified of their products, marketers should employ this strategy. Customers' loyalty will increase as a result. A new study suggests that anti-counterfeit marketing tactics should be adapted to different countries based on client perceptions of counterfeits. We wanted to find out how counterfeit items affect consumers' purchasing habits. Surveys were distributed to determine further the influence of counterfeit items on customer purchasing habits. We gathered the primary data using these questionnaires and then applied that data to the regression model. Consequently, we discovered that counterfeit goods and customer purchasing habits are not linked. In addition, there is a strong correlation between counterfeit items and consumer purchasing habits, such that a 1% rise in counterfeit products leads to a 15.7% increase in consumer purchasing habits. Because of this, the original brand manufacturers should be concerned about this problem and continue to introduce innovations into their goods and create fresh designs for consumers to avoid losing their clients, who will instead turn to counterfeit items.

Conclusion and Limitations

Conclusion

In this study, the purchase patterns of customers were evaluated in relation to the prevalence of counterfeit items. Questionnaires were addressed to the general community in order to acquire a better understanding of

how counterfeit products influence consumer purchasing habits. In order to assess survey-collected primary data, a regression model was utilized. It is safe to argue that consumer purchasing behaviors and counterfeit items are inextricably linked, as they cannot be separated. According to a study published in the Journal of Consumer Research in 2012, consumer purchasing behavior increases by 69 percent for every one percentage point increase in sales of counterfeit goods. A survey and data collection indicates that customers of authentic companies are increasingly opting for counterfeit goods. Original brand creators should continue to innovate and provide new ideas.

This study explored a variety of variables to determine whether customers were willing to purchase counterfeit items. Despite the growing problem of counterfeit luxury products in emerging nations and around the world, the demand side of the market for counterfeit luxury goods has received inadequate attention. We were able to find previously unknown socioeconomic and demographic factors that influence the purchase of counterfeit goods in developing countries. As a result of this study, original brand product marketers in developing nations will be able to demonstrate the originality of their items to their customers. Consider both the brand's reputation and the financial status of the target population when developing a company's marketing plan (Osman Gani et al., 2019).

Based on the above analysis, we've decided that hypothesis H0 has been rejected and that hypothesis H1 has been accepted since there is a substantial correlation between the purchase of counterfeit goods and consumer purchasing behavior after performing this study and examining all the findings and data. When it comes to creating awareness about counterfeit items, makers of branded products should use social media and other social networks. Items must be made so that a knock-off is impossible to produce. In this approach, customers would choose to purchase genuine brands rather than counterfeit ones. The cost of their items may also be reduced so that a buyer on a modest budget can acquire the originals. There were only a few questions regarding the measured variable's demand, despite other survey questions referencing this fact. Due to the limited variables, responses on demand may be biased if respondents misunderstand or misinterpret the question. Future research should employ a range of markers to ensure their validity.

Limitations

This study has some limitations. Due to the cross-sectional nature of this study, it was unable to confirm the causal evidence created by the analyzed components. This research also aimed to determine whether or not Pakistani consumers would purchase counterfeit luxury goods based on the five characteristics given above. Only these five criteria were anticipated to significantly influence the purchasing decisions of Pakistani consumers. Adding more variables to future studies could assist participants in evaluating the numerous influencing elements and reaching a more accurate result. Due to the small sample size, it is impossible to extrapolate the findings to further respondents. There are numerous applications for the findings of this study. It is possible to undertake in-depth research on a range of product categories, including luxury products, retail goods, and everyday essentials. Due to the likelihood that these hurdles would rationally support their findings, it is anticipated that research into the reasons why individuals in impoverished countries purchase counterfeit luxury products will continue.

This inquiry has a rather limited scope. Our survey participants were actual customers of physical companies. It is essential to remember that the vast majority of fraudulent transactions occur online. According to a new study, internet shopping patterns for outdoor products may vary (Chiu et al., 2018). Customers that shop online may have different purchasing patterns than those who shop in a physical store. This study did not assess customers' interest and participation in outdoor activities, which could be significant purchase intent predictors. Future research should examine the demographics of persons who purchase counterfeit outdoor gear in order to better comprehend why individuals do so. In addition, the probe focused on counterfeit goods. Future studies could explore a variety of outdoor products to analyze the purchasing patterns of counterfeit goods. The TPB has neglected to consider the emotional, habitual, and motivational factors of customers while making choices (Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001). According to Perugini and Bagozzi (2001), an alternative social-psychological

model that addresses the shortcomings of the TPB, future study may employ the goal-directed behavior model to investigate how individuals purchase outdoor counterfeits (Chiu et al., 2018; Chiu and Choi, 2018).

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